

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

Community Cluster

Research Software Engineering (RSE)

Chairs: Florian Thiery (LEIZA); Lutz Schubert (CAA-DE)

SC Decision: 28.04.2023

Bodies Involved: TA1-5 plus div. Participants

External Linking: NFDI4Culture (TA3, Expert:innen Forum für nachhaltige Softwareentwicklung in NFDI4Culture), NFDI4Earth (IG Research Software), NFDI4Ing (SIG workflow tools); deRSE e.V., CAA International (SIG SSLA, Little Minions), AG Research Software Engineering in den Digital Humanities (DHD), Linked Pasts

Subject & Objective

The overarching goal of this cluster is the interdisciplinary exchange in developing sustainable research software, which itself and the research data produced with it FAIRedelt (FAIR and FAIR4RS) are sustainably available and as extensively reusable as possible. The cluster defines research software as software and tools used to generate, process, analyse, link or present research data. This includes statistical analyses, e.g. with R and Python, or the visualisation of geo or 3D data in web platforms. The CC deals with the following topics: Research Software Engineering, development and further development of sustainable FAIRification tools, and RSE in research and teaching.

Out of Scope

This CC does not deal with proprietary software or software engineering that contradicts the Open Science concept. In addition, the (further) development of "N4O Core Services" is not part of the work of this cluster.

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Intended Work Results

The following work results are aimed at TWGs:

Object and collection-related sciences

- Whitepaper on "Coding in the object and collection sciences"
- Common guidelines / recommendations / best practices for the development and structuring of code and associated data
- Open Educational Resources for Coding in the Object and Collection Sciences

In General

- Concepts for the sustainability of research software and software solutions in a scientific context
- (Further) development of guidelines for sustainable research software
- Community building & interacting